

Immersive Experience- A Boon or Curse for Healthcare Professionals?

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Abstract: Innovative technologies are being used by medical professionals to accelerate the discovery of solutions to many disease threats. Virtual reality, augmented reality, and other immersive experiences play a crucial part in combating any challenging medical issue through audio-visual-based virtual communication. With the aid of online resources, a quick evaluation research on immersive technology and its uses in medical procedures is conducted in this article. Raising people's awareness of any critical situation makes it advantageous for remote locations to investigate telemedicine, and plan, treat, and control various medical conditions. With effective practical application of such technologies, researchers, doctors, the government, and academicians may create a healthy environment to combat the adverse medical crisis. These technologies created a platform to lessen the face-to-face interaction of clinicians even during the pandemic crisis like Covid 19 years.

Practical Implications: Given the significant role these technologies can play in many medical treatments of many patients; more research is required to define all potential fields in which immersive technologies can be applied.

Keywords: Augmented reality; Healthcare; Immersive experience; Virtual reality

1. Introduction

The rapid advancements in medical practices and product development in the twenty-first century are making people's lives healthier. However, they also provide a new challenge: instructing medical professionals on how to use this frequently complex technology. Healthcare practitioners always search for cutting-edge innovations to enhance their working process and environment (Andrews et al. 2019). They usually adopt new technologies first, enhancing their profession and patient experience. Virtual reality (VR) and Augmented reality (AR) have been widely used in the healthcare industry for various applications. By addressing current issues like the lack of qualified medical professionals, diagnostic errors, and underdiagnoses, VR and AR may improve clinical diagnosis and screening services in different medical fields. It is much like other technologies like telemedicine and artificial intelligence (Ma et al. 2022). VR was helpful in remote locations for telemedicine research, planning, therapy, and infection prevention by raising people's awareness of the disease. By reducing face-to-face interactions between clinicians and COVID-19 patients, VR technology created a platform to enhance surveillance systems for current events. (Singh et al. 2020). VR is frequently combined with the term AR. AR enhances user perception and makes something visible that would not otherwise be visible by superimposing computer-generated images onto the real world. VR simultaneously stimulates the user's senses and simulates the outside world using computer graphic systems, creating a digital, artificial environment (Park et al. 2020). Certain emergency surgical operations like accidents or trauma surgery cases are infrequently performed, and training with AR, VR, and MR may be beneficial. These computer-assisted techniques may eventually displace the use of human cadavers in training (Mackenzie et al. 2022).

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1.1 Immersive Technologies and healthcare

In the world of technology, VR & AR has emerged as prominent invention. VR technology uses wearable screens in VR headsets to immerse the user in a synthetic three-dimensional (3D) environment. Through the use of Head Mounted Displays (HMD) and specific tools and approaches, VR and AR technologies give users fully immersive experiences (Jangra et al. 2022). VR is a concept that has evolved over the last 50 years. Personalized immersive technology-driven devices have been on the market for several years and are constantly improving and growing. The user can interact with the virtual environment by using hand-held devices such as joysticks or keyboards and, more recently, integrated body tracking technologies (Cipresso et al. 2018). The first VR-based environment for learning and performing surgical procedures was developed in the 1990s. It was noted that VR was a very economical method that enabled medical students to recognize and reduce mistakes that could arise at any point in their education. VR was also used in physical rehabilitation in the 20th century when it was again shown to be a technique of the highest quality and effectiveness (Samadbeik et al. 2018). In the context of immersive technology, the term "extended reality" is frequently used to refer to augmented, virtual, and mixed worlds (AR, VR, and MR). Regarding accessibility, remoteness, and safety, each of these technologies opens up a range of possibilities for healthcare. Whether it be virtual or physical reality, each offers unique characteristics to improve performance and learning processes.

Hyper-realistic experiences can now be created very smoothly, thanks to significant advancements in software engines like Unity, Blender, Unreal, and others (Koppaka 2022). It is now possible to reproduce entire operating rooms with full sound, functional and responsive equipment, lifelike virtual patients, hand tracking, and realistic procedure interactions. The immersive solutions enable healthcare professionals to gather performance data, analyze it, evaluate it and give feedback. Healthcare professions have been made more hassle-free, accessible, and feasible by developing VR headgear, like the Oculus, Varjo XR-3, and VR Box-Smart Glasses, to name a few. Within minutes, VR enables professionals to immerse themselves and feel the experience in virtual worlds (Mao et al. 2021).

According to experts, immersive experiences will become increasingly important for medical teaching and learning, like how it has evolved in laparoscopic and robotic surgery techniques that require new and precise skill sets in the future (Winkler-Schwartz et al. 2019). Numerous recent technological developments have significantly impacted the development and practice of dentistry. Because they alter the patient experience, AR and virtual reality VR are increasingly popular in modern dentistry. Different scientific fields have benefited from AR and VR, but their application in dentistry has yet to be thoroughly investigated, and traditional dental practices are still widely used. Technology advancements have significantly changed dental treatment over the past few years. AR and VR systems in dentistry are still relatively new (Monterubbianesi et al. 2022).

The primary use of such technologies is to provide the user with an interface that seems like a simulator. According to the Harvard Business Review, a study at the University of California, Los Angeles, discovered that medical students who learned with VR tools completed an orthopedic procedure. Compared to the traditionally trained group, students in the VR group consistently scored much higher, with a total score improvement of 230%. The process was finished on average 20% more quickly by VR-trained participants than by those who received standard training. Additionally, they correctly completed 38% more of the steps on the procedure-specific checklist. There was statistical significance for both results (Blumstein 2019). Comparing these immersive technologies to traditional teaching and training positively affects medical education. Such learning processes were met with tremendous learner enthusiasm and enjoyment (Barteit et al. 2021). It was faster than those in the traditionally trained group — and they completed more steps correctly in the procedure-specific checklist. Several universities have used various immersive platforms where dedicated surgical simulation facilities are housed for better access and up-to-date instruments for the students (Car et al. 2020).

As a cutting-edge technology AR enriches the real environment by superimposing virtual things on it. In terms of surgical training and medical education, AR is adopting a basic and developing function. Since its implementation, students have a clearer understanding of the human body, and surgical simulations have helped them perform better (Cao et al. 2019). Its growing popularity is due to the ability it provides to observe and interact with digital items without having to turn away from the real world to view the monitor displaying the relevant medical imaging. Orthopaedics and oncology are the fields where AR is most frequently used because it enables accurate visualization of the anatomical structures and good control of the activities carried out during surgical resections (Wong et al. 2022).

The construction of the most entire healthcare experience has been made possible by the development of such immersive technology, which also enhances skill development and allows for remote access to training, eventually boosting patient safety. This review is significant because it shows how much more study is needed on healthcare experiences in realistic virtual settings.

2. Scopes and Limitations

There are currently limitations, with immersive technologies only being able to be used for short periods before becoming heavy or uncomfortably hot. Although headsets in their current form are unlikely to be used, hand tracking could replace controllers in the operating room (Hayes 2019). One of the major challenges with their use in the healthcare industry has been noted to be the effects of teleconsultation and immersive applications on in-person interactions and professional relationships between the doctor and patient.

The advancements made in the medicinal field towards the use of immersive technologies have been highly beneficial to surgeons in; their use as a simulator/in learning as well as for practice when there are no opportunities for them to practice physically. According to the review, immersive technologies allow a better understanding of a real-life medical condition by accompanying essential atmospheres, such as the holding of different instruments and the feel of what effect a tool has on a specific body part, along with sounds and vibrations. All the features seem necessary for practicing/learning for medical practitioners and students, as has been proven by a study conducted in research. Such technologies have also been proven to show their effects on COVID-19 and the different medical practices accompanying the pandemic. The field of technology is advancing, and these have brought quite an impact all over the world. Selecting the appropriate immersive technology can improve performance and learning because the options are limitless.

3. Conclusion

A virtual and augmented reality that has virtually permeated every aspect of our lives is a phenomenon of the new millennium. These technologies have seen the most widespread application in entertainment through immersive movies and video games. They also managed to develop technologies in healthcare, education, and worker training in addition to research. Both virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) have many uses, and their market potential is still expanding. Health care is one such important sector. Clinical experience and intuition are essentially irreplaceable. However, immersive reality has proven to be resilient and beneficial over time and especially in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, restrictions have been put in place that impedes the creation of accessible, inexpensive, and acceptable immersive resources for surgical education worldwide.

The next concern is how to employ immersive methodologies, tried-and-true co-creation techniques, and collaborative structures in healthcare curricula and practices in the most effective way possible. Surgery will alter the world even though a well-designed immersive reality won't completely satisfy training for the broad breadth of complexity in surgical and other essential care needed for optimal outcomes. It will revitalize interest and aspiration for the next generation of medical practitioners regardless of where they are in the world.

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